

Paper 10**CURIOSITY AMONG VISUALLY IMPAIRED ADOLESCENTS****Buvana R^{1*} & KT Shwetha²**¹Research Scholar, College of Social Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, IndiaOrcidID: 0000-0003-1761-428X; E-mail: buvanar@hotmail.com

Mobile: 9945760150

²Assistant Professor, College of Social Science, Srinivas University, Mangalore, IndiaOrcidID: 0000-0003-0895-6333; E-mail: ktshwetha@gmail.com

Mobile: 9902322985

ABSTRACT

Purpose: Curiosity is a strong desire to learn new things. This subjective trait or quality is stronger in children than adults. This study aims to understand the curiosity among visually impaired (VI) adolescent children. Curiosity and Explorative Inventory (CEI-II) would examine the exploratory nature and absorption nature of the minds of VI children. Curiosity plays a major role in learning and retention. Tolman and Honzk (1930) investigated latent learning in rats through the maze experiment. This paved the way to several research on curiosity and motivation. The ability and the sense of sight triggers a multitude of thoughts in a human mind. When there is low vision or blindness, what would be the difference in their approach towards curiosity? The exploratory nature of curiosity of a VI person could become a factor for personal growth. This study could throw light on the nature of embracing new ideas and learning new things as opposed to being absorbed in activities. They could potentially tell us more about the inhibitions, knowledge, motivation, interests, etc. of VI children. The level of curiosity, the triggers behind those curious thoughts could be potential areas of study for future researchers.

Design/Methodology/Approach: This experimental study would be based on a group of children who are visually impaired.

Findings/Result: This hypothetical research aims at determining if there is any significance in the trait curiosity among visually impaired adolescent children. The explorative and absorption nature of adolescents, who are visually impaired, has not been studied before which can be examined in this study.

Originality/Value: Curiosity trait among visually impaired children in an Indian context that has not yet been explored is being experimented in this study.

Paper Type: Experimental and analysis based paper.

Keywords: Curiosity, CEI, VI, Visual Impairment, Blind, Adolescents

1. INTRODUCTION

“The most beautiful thing in the world cannot be seen or touched, they can only be felt in the heart”-Helen Keler. Globally there are about 2.2 billion who have near or distant visual impairment. The prevalence of the impairment in India is about less than 2% of the population of India. The classification of visual impairment may be moderate, severe, profound or legally blind based on the vision loss. Curiosity in Wikipedia states that Curiosity is a strong desire to know or learn about something. Curiosity is the inquisitive thinking that can explore, learn and

investigate more about something. Some observers feel that curiosity is more of information seeking in a broader sense. Curiosity has been a fascinating subject for many in the research field. Curiosity is a fundamental component of human intellect, yet its biological role, methods, and brain underpinnings are still unknown. It is, nevertheless, a learning motivator and influencer [1]. Curiosity has been extensively researched in the context of accomplishing tasks with limited rewards. In the authors' opinion, it serves two important purposes. Curiosity assists an agent in exploring its environment in search of new knowledge—a desired quality of exploratory behavior is that it will improve as the agent learns more. Furthermore, curiosity is a means for an agent to gain new abilities. That might come in handy in the future. Curiosity is regarded as a powerful driver of learning. Learning may appear to be increased since we are most interested in the knowledge that we are going to learn. Thus, rather than curiosity naturally promoting learning, the apparent increase to learning may be driven by one's past knowledge, or there may be a feedback loop between the two aspects [2]. Being curious and being creative go hand in hand. Children are highly curious when most learning happens. Some children have an eye for potentially important things by being curious. Many remarkable observations or inventions are created benefiting humanity. Teachers facilitate and encourage curiosity from an early age. If properly nourished, new initiatives, skilled approaches, lateral and critical thinking can be well developed by the teachers. Hands on, practical knowledge with an inquisitive thinking sparks new ideas building an ability to supplement in the problem-solving, decision-making processes. In the past, being curious was considered inquisitive along the lines of vice. The need for curiosity in acquiring new knowledge and other aspects, the role has changed from vice to virtue. Research finds that curiosity has significant effects on memory among 7 and 8 year olds [3]. A study which is based on prior knowledge theory as a contributing factor to curiosity has in fact revealed results showing that there is a significant relationship between curiosity and memory regions in our brain. Their research shows heightened curiosity levels enhance learning [4]. Hope being a psychological asset was studied with curiosity as a predictor with few other predictors like self-efficacy, self-construal and decisiveness. For this study however, the relevance of curiosity is to be understood. The above study found that curiosity had no role to play as a predictor [5]. It makes one wonder at the thought of could being curious make oneself happy? Many studies are available to see the relevance between curiosity and academic achievement. This particular study was based in India among high school children and there seems to be a positive relationship between curiosity and happiness [6]. People's curiosity towards scientific solutions might be influenced by their social context. Participants were provided daily scientific questions from a prominent online forum, and they were offered the choice to divulge a selection of them. Participants were more interested in the answers to questions with a high (vs. low) number of up-votes. These effects were somewhat mediated by surprise and the assumed utility of information, with a stronger influence from surprise. These social construct based studies result in triggering curiosity among us. The interesting findings indicate that popularity's principal impact was to lower interest about less popular issues rather than to boost curiosity about more popular ones. Perhaps popularity acts as a clue for determining what not to learn more about rather than a cue for determining what to pursue [7]. Children are inquisitive beings. They investigate, question, and wonder, learning about the moment of birth, and maybe even before. Humans are naturally drawn to new experiences. When we are intrigued by something new, we want to learn more about it. And it is during exploring that we make discoveries. Our life would be boring if we did not have creativity. It is via

imagination, and imagination plays a huge part. Any accomplishment owes a great deal to the ability to imagine [8]. The Indian government recently released National Education Policy (NEP) 2019, a critical policy framework for structuring education, Curiosity is expressly mentioned as an important attribute for children to acquire in the country's education system (MHRD, 2018). The NEP requests that "puzzles" be included into the curriculum in the context of teaching mathematics, language, logic, and creativity. It encourages better play and for pupils under the age of eight, discovery-based learning is used. In Karnataka this is the nali kali method for preschoolers. The National Education Policy additionally implies that science in vernacular compared to the English language is today of worse quality, and the majority of pupils do not gain adequate competency [9]. Undergraduate college students were studied to understand the relationship between life satisfaction, gratitude and curiosity. Gratitude was positively significant with curiosity. Girls scored more than the boys showing satisfaction scales tipping to their side [10]. An intervention based - a fresh method of stimulating interest - changing the perceived worth of a topic. It was explicitly investigated whether altering the perceived worth of a topic could elicit curiosity. The popularity of a scientific issue might also influence people's interest in that subject. If such a value modification influences curiosity, then interventions on value may have significant consequences not only for curiosity researchers, but also for science. The project resulted in a more successful technique. To pique people's interest is to provide information in a way that allows them to immediately understand its worth and importance rather than presenting interesting information [11].

A person is considered legally blind in India when the field of vision is less than 20 degrees or the eyesight is lesser than or equal to 20/200 based on the Snellan chart. This study aims to study the curiosity level of the visually impaired high school children. A total of 4,029 pupils from nine schools were tested in Hyderabad. The average age of the children was 9.33.4 years, ranging from 3 to 18 years. There were 2,348 male children (58.3 percent) and 1,681 girls (41.7 percent). Hyperopia was prevalent at 22.6 percent, myopia at 8.6 percent, and astigmatism at 10.3 percent. Myopia was substantially more prevalent in children aged 10 years [12]. Another study examined the teaching of life sciences (biology) to blind and visually impaired students in 11 special schools in South Africa, with a focus on the development of science process skills in outcomes-based classrooms. Individual structured interviews were done with nine scientific educators from the various special schools, as well as focus group interviews with 10 Grade 12 students from each of the schools. The study indicated that learners struggled to apply science process skills due to a lack of vision, confidence, motivation, and so on [13]. In a polish blind school, a total of about 11500 students learnt a foreign language. It was identified that they had the necessary skills and they were in no way lesser than sighted students in their interest and motivation to learn something new. This shows that VI students have greater potential and motivation to learn [14]. Curiosity can be elicited based on five main principles namely novelty, partial exposure, complexity, uncertainty and conflict. They were analyzed with fourteen different behavioral indicators and multi modalities. A couple of educational areas seem to be significant with trait curiosity enhancing learning [15]. Similar eliciting of information as stated above is being studied as first person cues, third person cues and future oriented cues. Children in general want to find out reasons, causes for a multitude of things and their question is always 'why'. This explanation seeking behavior and motivational drive of curiosity contributes majorly towards children's learning [16]. Eight different behaviors were discovered through

classroom observations as approaches for instructors to foster a curious classroom atmosphere. For example, when students are more at ease with uncertainty, they are more likely to strive to figure out what they don't know rather than being afraid of being wrong. Students must have the chance to think, question, and engage in order to perceive ambiguity, and they must believe that they are expected to do so. Children teamed up for different activities in order to experience the above [17]. Not long ago research was majorly carried out by going to the libraries. The myriad of knowledge and materials that could be found in actual articles, journals, books and previous research papers etc., was extraordinary. The advancement of technology has bestowed upon us an ocean of reference materials available at our fingertips. The role of libraries and librarians, undeniably played a major role in cultivating the element of curiosity among children. Engagement with learning and disengagement from learning based on the teaching method, style and depth of learning makes one curious resulting in different kinds of research papers [18]. Curiosity based learning (CBL) method is the latest method that the student teachers are trained with for the bachelor's program. This method is where the teacher is the center for all learning, facilitating the teaching learning process. This CBL as opposed to the Inquiry based model is what the Indian education system used to be. Students learning is greater involving a sharing of curiosity and increase in curiosity. The benefits seem to be more which keeps the students engaged and involved in class [19]. Creative self- efficacy (CSE) and Creative Personal Identity (CPI) were analyzed against the curiosity inventory and there was a strong correlation between them. It showed that CSE has more significance against curiosity showing a dominant creative nature in both [20]. Based on the above reviews and data from previous research, it is found that curiosity helps in academic achievement, personal growth, motivation, self-confidence etc. Since there is no sufficient evidence in the curiosity levels of visually impaired children, this study aims to bridge the gap by determining the difference in the curiosity levels of both sighted and non-sighted adolescent children. In a unique study of visual impaired children learning through art, formulation strategies based on investigation via the original question of artistic creation was required for the process of transferring knowledge and skills from the production of art experiments. People with low eyesight do research by fumbling and peering closely, whereas people with near-blindness and absolute blindness processed information through touch and hearing. Near-blind persons made an effort to perceive differently to aim the light source as directly as possible onto the item, but persons who are completely blind utilize constantly sniff items to comprehend them specifically [21]. In workshops conducted on body awareness among blind people, men showed more curiosity and touched female models whereas women were less curious and were apprehensive to even explore and touch the models. They were curious to know more about their gender, menstruation, pregnancy but not on sexuality or pleasures [22]. Curiosity among visually impaired children in the field of science is more but less accessible because of the many abstract concepts. They need to explore by touching and feeling in a tactile method to examine models to help them in understanding the concepts [23].

2. METHODOLOGY

(a) Hypothesis: H_0 : There is no significant difference between curiosity levels among adolescent children of sighted and visually impaired school students.

(b) Tool: CEI-II Inventory [26], IBM SPSS, MS Office

(c) **Sample Size:** The total number of adolescent children were 100. A total of 50 sighted and 50 visually impaired students participated in the study. All of them belonged to the same demographic background and same ethnicity.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

An Independent Sample 't' Test was processed and analyzed with the data collected and following two tables are displayed as outcomes. The 50 children from each group, a total of 100 children, as mentioned by the author of the tool, were divided as a two factor model, one for the motivation to seek out knowledge and new experiences which is termed as "Stretching" and a willingness to embrace the novel, uncertain, and unpredictable nature of everyday life is termed as "Embracing" [26]. Seeking information in new situations, performing best in challenging situations, finding opportunities to learn and grow in such circumstances and self-reflections during and after, are the highlights of this inventory. Visually impaired students (V) have a higher mean of 21.2 than the sighted students (S) in such scenarios. After interacting with the bunch of them, it is a privilege to state that they carry themselves with high self-esteem. Many of them consider and use opportunities as something new and challenging. They like to approach situations with a brave stride without much fear. On the other hand, the 50 children who are sighted have a far lesser mean of 15.4. Their approach is more on a cautious scale. It makes one wonder and also opens up possibilities for future research to find out why such a difference exists. Could it be that they are intimidated at trying out newer things? Are they less confident because they have eyesight? That they can literally see around and become demotivated, scared and skeptical? Embracing new ideas, events, unfamiliar people, etc is the very backbone of the students for the second factor in this two factor model of the inventory.

Being adventurous and daring, doing exciting, frightening things, things that are uncertain and unpredictable can be easy to handle for some students. With the visually impaired, this factor again seems to be on a higher scale than the sighted children. The mean is 19.700 although making it lesser than their stretching score. Could it be that they are self-aware of their limitations and hence affected the score to some extent? This means however is definitely higher than the sighted students' score which means that the curious nature of the adventurous spirit is more in the VI students. Again, it is curious to know the reason behind this difference. It is found that there is not much variance for situations that are unpredictable, frightening and challenging between the two groups. Table 4 gives item wise t-test significance data. The t test run on independent samples which gives the following result. Total Mean of Sighted Children: 30.98, Total Mean of Visually Impaired children: 40.90, 1. The critical value for $df(98) = 1.984$, $T \text{ value} = 12.596 > 1.984$, $P \text{ value} < 0.001$, Confidence Interval is between .787 and 8.357 and does not cross zero. Hence based on the above criteria, the null hypothesis is thus rejected. This results in the visually impaired children's curiosity levels as not being equal to the curiosity levels of those of sighted children. There is a significant difference between their curiosity levels. VI students, with higher level of curiosity, and from the above reviews of literature, is it safe to assume that this may have direct correlation to their academic performance, well-being, happiness, positive outlook, etc. When this is applied with collaborated facilitation by the special education teachers, it may be highly beneficial for the children. Increased motivation, experiential learning can be experienced by children with proper guidance and facilitation.

4. CONCLUSION:

Visually challenged students have exclusive online library for them that could answer many of their curiosity related questions. This initiative was started by the Government of India with having a strong understanding about the needs and perception of people with VI. Suganya Pustakalaya has a vision and good scope that needs to spread throughout the nation [24]. Lack of intrinsic motivation and discouragement from family members act as barriers for VI people to have regular exercise and walking [25]. Dedicated phone apps for different purposes aiding their daily living are available for free downloads. Percentage of curiosity at different levels could also be satiated through these apps. Online books and phone apps through smartphones are a boon to people with visual impairments. The aim of the study was to understand the curiosity level of visually impaired adolescent students. Data was collated and compared with curiosity levels of sighted school students and it resulted in rejecting the null hypothesis proving that there does exist a significant difference in the difference between the curiosity levels between the groups. Curiosity could be a factor to motivate the kids to learn, assimilate and remember. There is room for an increase in attention and cognition. Furthermore, it could help them shape up their personality and increase their confidence.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Kidd, C., & Hayden, B. Y. (2015). The psychology and neuroscience of curiosity. *Neuron*, 88(3), 449-460.
- [2] Pathak, D., Agrawal, P., Efron, A. A., & Darrell, T. (2017, July). Curiosity-driven exploration by self-supervised prediction. In *International conference on machine learning*, 2778-2787.
- [3] Walin, H., & Xu, F. (2016, January). Curiosity and its influence on children's memory. In *Proceedings of the 38th Annual Conference of the Cognitive Science Society*, 872-876.
- [4] Wade, S., & Kidd, C. (2019). The role of prior knowledge and curiosity in learning. *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, 26(4), 1377-1387.
- [5] Öztekin, H. R., & Bayraktar, F. (2019). How Decisiveness, Self-Efficacy, Curiosity and Independent and Interdependent Self-Construals Are Related to Future Hopefulness among Senior Students. *Behavioral Sciences*, 9(12), 154-165.
- [6] Banupriya, V., & Rajan, M. R. (2019). Curiosity, Happiness and Academic Achievement among High School Students, 7(2), 456-466.
- [7] Dubey, R., Mehta, H., & Lombrozo, T. (2021). Curiosity is contagious: A social influence intervention to induce curiosity. *Cognitive science*, 45(2), 1-16.
- [8] Kidd, C., & Hayden, B. Y. (2015). The psychology and neuroscience of curiosity. *Neuron*, 88(3), 449-460.
- [9] Singh, A., & Manjaly, J. A. (2022). Using curiosity to improve learning outcomes in schools. *SAGE Open*, 12(1), 69392-9393
- [10] Biber, D., & Brandenburg, G. (2021). Understanding Gratitude, Curiosity and Life Satisfaction in College. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies in Education*, 10(2), 65-80.
- [11] Dubey, R., Griffiths, T., & Lombrozo, T. (2019). If it's important, then I am curious: A value intervention to induce curiosity. *Cognitive Science*, 282-288.
- [12] Kalikivayi, V., Naduvilath, T. J., Bansal, A. K., & Dandona, L. (1997). Visual impairment in school children in southern India. *Indian Journal of ophthalmology*, 45(2), 129-130.
- [13] Fraser, W. J., & Maguvhe, M. O. (2008). Teaching life sciences to blind and visually impaired learners. *Journal of Biological Education*, 42(2), 84-89.

- [14] Jedynek, M. (2010). Foreign Language Motivation-Some Deliberations on its Enhancement in Visually Impaired Learners. *Anglica Wratislaviensia*, 48, 171-182.
- [15] Nojavanasghari, B., Baltrusaitis, T., Hughes, C. E., & Morency, L. P. (2016). The Future Belongs to the Curious: Towards Automatic Understanding and Recognition of Curiosity in Children. In *WOCCI*, 16-22.
- [16] Liquin, E. G., & Lombrozo, T. (2020). Explanation-seeking curiosity in childhood. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 35, 14-20.
- [17] Jirout, J. J., Vitiello, V. E., & Zumbunn, S. K. (2018). Curiosity in schools. *The new science of curiosity*, 243-266.
- [18] Roberts, L. W., Keller, C. R., & Welsh, M. E. (2022). Spark: Students Describe Curiosity and Passion for Learning. *portal: Libraries and the Academy*, 22(3), 613-630.
- [19] Binson, B. (2009). Curiosity-Based Learning (CBL) Program. *Online Submission*, 6(12), 13-22.
- [20] Karwowski, M. (2012). Did curiosity kill the cat? Relationship between trait curiosity, creative self-efficacy and creative personal identity. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 8(4), 547-558.
- [21] Fajrie, N., Rohidi, T. R., Syakir, M., Syarif, I., & Priyatmojo, A. S. (2020). A study of visual impairment in the art creation process using clay. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 11(10), 199-218.
- [22] Goyal, N. (2017). Denial of sexual rights: insights from lives of women with visual impairment in India. *Reproductive health matters*, 25(50), 138-146.
- [23] Kizilaslan, A. (2019). Linking Theory to Practice: Science for Students with Visual Impairment. *Science Education International*, 30(1), 56-64.
- [24] Dodamani, A. M., & Gedam, S. (2017). USERS' AWARENESS OF SUGAMYA PUSTAKALAYA: AN ONLINE LIBRARY FOR THE VISUALLY CHALLENGED IN INDIA. *Library of Progress-Library Science, Information Technology & Computer*, 37(2).
- [25] India, G., Jain, M., Karya, P., Diwakar, N., & Swaminathan, M. (2021, October). VStroll: An audio-based virtual exploration to encourage walking among people with vision impairments. In *The 23rd International ACM SIGACCESS Conference on Computers and Accessibility* (pp. 1-13).
- [26] Kashdan, T. B., Gallagher, M. W., Silvia, P. J., Winterstein, B. P., Breen, W. E., Terhar, D., & Steger, M. F. (2009). The curiosity and exploration inventory-II: Development, factor structure, and psychometrics. *Journal of research in personality*, 43(6), 987-998.